

Improving Non-Oncology Provider Knowledge of Immunotherapy Adverse Events

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Background

- Exponential increase in use of checkpoint inhibitors (CIs) for cancer treatment
- Some immunotherapy agents (e.g., PD-1, CTLA-4) employ checkpoint receptors to support activation/suppression of T cell function leading to effective attacks on malignant cells but also an auto-immune response, whereby normal tissues are also attacked
- Adverse events (AEs) may be difficult to diagnose and manage
- This makes education of non-oncology providers vital so they may understand how CIs work and how to manage these AEs

Purpose

- This project aimed to educate non-oncology providers in a community hospital about newly developed clinical guidelines specific to CI AEs and evaluate knowledge changes related to identification and management of CI-related AEs.
- A 2nd aim was to determine whether patient outcomes related to adverse CI events were handled appropriately

Method

- Knowledge pretest/posttest
- Micro-Teaching, 7 to 10-minute educational in-services, to RNs and MDs
- Content - recognition of AEs (particularly colitis and pneumonitis) and management according to nationally published guidelines
- Micro-Teaching tailored to either RNs or MDs

Conceptual Framework

Results

Table 1 All RNs

	Pre N=129	Post N=125	P
Are you familiar with immunotherapy as a treatment for cancer?	51.9% (67) Yes	96.8% (121) Yes	<.0001
Are you familiar with national guidelines for the management of immunotherapy adverse events?	8.5% (11)	90.4% (113)	<.0001
Are you familiar with the intervention(s) needed to start reversing most immunotherapy adverse events?	14% (18)	96% (120)	<.0001
Immunotherapy and chemotherapy may be administered simultaneously.	52.7% (68)	89.6% (112)	<.0001
Neutropenic patients who are receiving chemotherapy can be treated with steroids.	49.6% (64)	95.2% (119)	<.0001

Table 2 Oncology RNs

	Pre N=13 Yes	Post N=12 Yes	P
Are you familiar with immunotherapy as a treatment for cancer?	92.3% (12)	91.7% (11)	0.953
Are you familiar with national guidelines for the management of immunotherapy adverse events?	23.1% (3)	75% (9)	0.006
Are you familiar with the intervention(s) needed to start reversing most immunotherapy adverse events?	46.2% (6)	83.3% (10)	0.083
Immunotherapy and chemotherapy may be administered simultaneously.	69.2% (9)	91.7% (11)	0.273
Neutropenic patients who are receiving chemotherapy can be treated with steroids.	69.2% (9)	91.7% (11)	0.273

Results

- Percentage of nurses who correctly responded to 5 knowledge items increased after teaching sessions, $p < .001$
- Baseline nurse knowledge of interventions to reverse CI AEs was low; 14% correctly responded compared to 96% after education.
- Baseline knowledge of oncology nurses was higher than for other nurses but with instruction, they increased in knowledge about CI AE guidelines and interventions

Key Learnings

- Tailoring brief presentations to audiences (RN vs MD) in small groups (2-8 participants) in the practice setting was effective
- Patient outcomes were not easy to extract from existing EHR; involving IT in the planning phase would improve likelihood of accurate extraction; need to foresee future IT projects that could become barrier
- Further staff knowledge gaps were identified in EHR audit

Recommendations

- Micro-Teaching intervention needs further testing
- Increasing complexity of oncology treatments require education and engagement of non-oncology providers for AE collaborative management
- For future projects, the team should work with clinical informatics regarding upcoming updates or changes that could affect a project